

Russia-affiliated scholars publishing about internationalisation of higher education

A quantitative investigation based on Web of Science and OpenAlex

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This note is best viewed on-line at the following link:

<https://giorgiocomai.eu/post/2025-06-wos-openalex-internationalisation-higher-education-russia/>

A preliminary note

This research note relies on a combination of Clarivate's Web of Science (henceforth, WoS) and OpenAlex to address the same question previously explored based on Scopus (see also as a pdf stored on Zenodo with a stable DOI 10.5281/zenodo.14791245) - or OpenAlex alone (see also as a pdf stored on Zenodo with a stable DOI 10.5281/zenodo.15722294).

Objective of this research note

Outline trends in the publication record of Russia-affiliated scholars writing about internationalisation of higher education.

Why a combination of Web of Science and OpenAlex

As this author currently does not have access to the (costly) "Web of Science Expanded API", this analysis relies on "Web of Science Starter API", accessed through the "Institutional Member Plan".

WoS Starter API allow to retrieve only basic metadata about publications; unfortunately, this does not include information about affiliation of authors that would make it possible to filter by country of affiliation.

As this information is necessary for the purpose of this analysis, the information retrieved from the WoS API is combined with information available through OpenAlex by matching DOIs of publications.

For a debate of the usefulness of combining information retrieved from different bibliometric APIs, see in particular Velez-Estevez et al. (2023). For a comparison of OpenAlex, Scopus and WoS, see Culbert et al. (2025).

Due to data availability issues and mismatches between the different datasets, part of the data needs to be discarded, but even considering these limitations, the approach should remain substantively meaningful.

The approach, in practice

The following sections detail all data processing steps, including all issues that determine the exclusion of part of the items originally retrieved from WoS.

Step 1: retrieve data from WoS Starter API

The following queries are given to the WoS APIs:

```
[1] "TS=(\"higher education\" AND internationalisation) AND PY=2011-2024 AND DT=Article'
```

```
[2] "TS=(\"higher education\" AND internationalization) AND PY=2011-2024 AND DT=Article'
```

Based on available fields tags, this requests all items present in WoS that:

- have both “higher education” and “internationali(s|z)ation” in either Title, Abstract, Author keywords, or Keywords Plus
- have been published between 2011 and 2024
- have “Article” as Document type

These criteria reflect precisely the same criteria used in the previous analyses based on Scopus and OpenAlex.

These queries return 3 244 unique publications.

As we need to rely on DOIs to match these data with OpenAlex, we will need to drop all items that do not have a DOI, reducing the total to 2 864

	Year	No Ru affiliation	Ru affiliation	Affiliation NA	Total	Ru share
	2011	42	0	2	44	0.00%
	2012	37	2	2	41	0.08%
	2013	77	0	9	86	0.00%
	2014	81	0	8	89	0.00%
	2015	133	2	11	146	0.08%
	2016	181	2	16	199	0.08%
	2017	164	0	14	178	0.00%
	2018	213	6	17	236	0.23%
	2019	215	7	39	261	0.27%
	2020	202	9	25	236	0.35%
	2021	255	15	23	293	0.58%
	2022	290	2	23	315	0.08%
	2023	285	4	15	304	0.15%
	2024	310	2	79	391	0.08%
	NA	51	0	12	63	0.00%
Total	—	2536	51	295	2882	—

We can then query OpenAlex to retrieve all available information about this set of DOIs.

A small number of these DOIs are not available on OpenAlex, reducing the total to 2 882. Manual parsing could possibly allow to reduce slightly the number of missing matches, but considering the relatively small number of missing articles, this analysis will proceed based on a fully automated and reproducible approach.

OpenAlex would identify some of these items as something that is not a journal article (187 items in total), mostly categorising them as book chapters. It would also record the publication year before 2011 for 15 items. But for the purpose of this analysis, we will trust WoS and keep all items retrieved from WoS that match the above query, have a doi, and that doi corresponds to an item available on OpenAlex. The vast majority of items retrieved from WoS remain part of these analysis even accounting for data quality issues.

In brief, the 2 882 journal articles identified via WoS and available on OpenAlex include:

- 51 articles with at least an author with a Russian affiliation
- 2 536 articles with no author with a Russian affiliation
- 295 articles where the affiliation is not available (or, in a small number of cases, the country of the affiliation is not available)

Number of publications about internationalisation of higher education

Counting relevant journal publications identified by Web of Science

Affiliation attributed based on OpenAlex data

* 'Russian affiliation' attributed if at least one author is affiliated with a Russia-based institution
Not included when affiliation is not available or could not be attributed to any country.

Focus on publications by scholars with a Russian affiliation

N.B. the following tables report only data related to articles published with a Russian affiliation; if the same author has published other articles about internationalisation of higher education, but not with a Russian affiliation, this is not included in this section.

By author

Authors of scholarly articles associated with 'internationalisation of higher education' published with a Russian affiliation. Ordered by number of publications; click on the `cited by` column to order by number of times cited; as expected, OpenAlex and Web of Science report slightly different figures. The `works` column link to the page dedicated to the article on OpenAlex, including a complete set of metadata and a link to the article itself (usually, shown right under the title, as a button with "html" and/or "pdf").

Table 1: Authors of scholarly articles associated with ‘internationalisation of higher education’ published with a Russian affiliation. Including only authors with at least 3 publications or cited 10 times or more.

author	affiliation	items	cited by (WoS)	cited by (OpenAlex)	works
Andrey Baykov	Moscow State Institute of International Relations	5	12	16	W4389194816; W3200589657; W3215481495; W4206237913; W4283071963
Anne Crowley-Vigneau	Moscow State Institute of International Relations	4	12	15	W4389194816; W3200589657; W4206237913; W4283071963
Kseniya E. Kovalenko	Altai State University	3	3	4	W2896378813; W2931401133; W3014167476
Maria Yudkevich	National Research University Higher School of Economics	1	48	76	W933871197
Simon Marginson	National Research University Higher School of Economics	1	45	60	W3157988227
Галина Валентиновна Телегина	University of Tyumen	1	20	33	W2150097343
Irina B. Stukalova	Plekhanov Russian University of Economics	1	13	34	W1127500079
Anatoly Shishkin	Plekhanov Russian University of Economics	1	13	34	W1127500079
Anastasia Stukalova	Plekhanov Russian University of Economics	1	13	34	W1127500079
Natalya L. Antonova	Ural Federal University	1	12	24	W3005184604
Anastasia D. Sushchenko	Ural Federal University	1	12	24	W3005184604
Natalia G. Popova	Ural Branch of the Russian Academy of Sciences	1	12	24	W3005184604
Yelena Kalyuzhnova	Moscow State Institute of International Relations	1	12	15	W4206237913
Irina Petrovskaya	Lomonosov Moscow State University	1	11	18	W3015784306
Sergei Shaposhnikov	Lomonosov Moscow State University	1	11	18	W3015784306

By institution

Russian institutions where scholars who published about ‘internationalisation of higher education’ were affiliated with. Ordered by number of publications; click on the **cited by** column to order by number of times cited.

Table 2: Authors affiliated with these Russia-based institutions have published about ‘internationalisation of higher education’. Including only institutions with at least 3 publications or cited 10 times or more.

affiliation	cited by items (WoS)	cited by (OpenAlex)	works	
National Research University Higher School of Economics	7	102	150	W3157988227; W3174037697; W933871197; W3159305760; W3165946074; W3196622995; W4313562657
University of Tyumen	3	25	46	W2150097343; W2797683626; W3048896412
Ural Federal University	6	21	40	W2913302515; W3005184604; W3176232077; W3037257456; W3089114396; W4399284330
Moscow State Institute of International Relations	7	19	36	W3104147942; W4389194816; W2890250287; W3200589657; W3215481495; W4206237913; W4283071963
Ural Branch of the Russian Academy of Sciences	2	14	40	W3005184604; W2998243963
Plekhanov Russian University of Economics	1	13	34	W1127500079
St Petersburg University	4	13	25	W2793133357; W2912945906; W2928397659; W2997643514
Lomonosov Moscow State University	2	12	23	W2979473714; W3015784306
National Research Tomsk State University	5	7	9	W4307719949; W4253468041; W2724793034; W3133571340; W3164827087
Altai State University	3	3	4	W2896378813; W2931401133; W3014167476

References

Culbert, Jack H., Anne Hobert, Najko Jahn, Nick Haupka, Marion Schmidt, Paul Donner, and Philipp Mayr. 2025. ‘Reference Coverage Analysis of OpenAlex Compared to Web of Science and Scopus’. *Scientometrics* 130 (4): 2475–92. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11192-025-05293-3>.

Velez-Estevez, A., I. J. Perez, P. García-Sánchez, J. A. Moral-Munoz, and M. J. Cobo. 2023. ‘New Trends in Bibliometric APIs: A Comparative Analysis’. *Information Processing & Management* 60 (4): 103385. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ipm.2023.103385>.

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